

INNOVATIONS AND APPLICATIONS IN SAND CONTROL: A CRITICAL REVIEW

Eze Samuel Tochukwu

Department of Petroleum Engineering, Federal University of Technology Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>Sand production is one of the global documented hazard oil field passes through field development phase, and is often visible with oil and gas formation with unconsolidated sandstone. There is need to manage sand production for effective oil production. When the sand production issue is mismanaged, sand particles in the borehole starts accumulating, blocking the oil flow path, resulting in a rapid drop in the production capacity of oil and gas wells, and potentially leading to abrupt abandonment of the well. In this study, different sand control approaches were documented ranging from conventional to new techniques. From the result of the study, polymer-based solutions such as resin diversion technique and nanoparticle-based solution such as zeta potential sand control were identified as new methods for sand production control. The surface sand control systems were identified as excellent sand control for high pressure reservoir, while digital oilfield technology approach proved to be the best in sand prediction, monitoring and control.</p>	<p>Sand Production, Sand Production Control, Oil Production</p>

1.0. Overview of Sand Production in Oilfield

Sand production is one of the global documented hazard oilfields passes through field development phase, and is often visible with oil and gas formation with unconsolidated sandstone [1]. It occurs when the stress on the formation exceeds the formation strength, and usually yields rock failure. There is need to manage sand production for effective oil production. When the sand production issue is mismanaged, sand particles in the borehole starts accumulating, blocking the oil flow path, resulting in a rapid drop in the production capacity of oil and gas wells, and potentially leading to abrupt abandonment of the well. These have necessitated to comprehensive study the causes of sand production and the mechanism of sand control, and adopt effective sand management approach to lower the harm caused by sand production [2]. The production of sand impacts of oilfield operations with challenges such as erosion of downhole and surface equipment, formation subsidence, sand accumulation in surface equipment, subsurface accumulation and sand disposal. [3,4]. The negative impact have created the need for sand production evaluation using geological factors and production factors [5]. The

geological factors refers to the geologic condition within the well environment, and includes influence of rock physical properties, impact of formation pressure, impact of horizontal tectonic stress and impact of fluid properties [6,7]. The production factors refers to the direct impact of human activities on sand production in the formation [8], and it includes perforation impact [9], fluid extraction intensity impact [10], production dynamic pressure difference [11] and impact of changes in water-cut [12].

2.0. Sand Control Technologies

Sand production has adverse impact on oilfield activities, with the resultant yielding of downhole and surface erosion, formation subsidence and accumulation in surface treatment facilities [13]. The need to manage sand production has led to several innovative approaches such as traditional sand control method, fracture method and new approach [14].

2.1.Traditional Sand Control Approach

The traditional sand control approach dealt with the conventional methods utilized for sand control, and comprised of mechanical sand control, chemical sand control, coking sand control and composite sand control approaches [15]. Table 1 shows the concrete way and applicable condition for the various conventional sand control approaches.

Table 1: Adaptation condition of Sand Control Technology

Sand Control. Tech.	Concrete Way	Applicable Conditions
Mechanical Sand Control	Sand control pipe string technology	Suitable for heterogeneous reservoir, medium and coarse sand size
	Improved sand control pipe string technology	Not suitable for fine silty sand stratum with high mud content. Clay is easy to block gravel layer.
Chemical Sand Control	The artificial casing method	The reservoir with good reservoir homogeneity and small reservoir thickness
	Artificial cementation method	Fine silty sand to medium formation sand with good vertical permeability
		Sand control for small vertical well (side drilling) and high pressure well with casing perforation and completion
		Not suitable for high water cut period
Coking Sand Control	Hot air injection for sand fixation	It is mainly used for loose sandstone heavy oil reservoir with a density than $0.934g/cm^3$ by burning reservoir or steam injection
	Short-term in-situ combustion for oil layer sand fixation	Sand control wells should be far away from the boundary of oil and water, with high oil saturation (more than 40%) to prevent excessive heat loss.

2.1.1. Mechanical Sand Control

The mechanical sand control technique utilizes slotted liner, wire-wound screen and gravel pack to prevent formation sand bodies from entering the well bore [16, 17, 18]. In its application, there are two common forms: sand control pipe technology and improved sand control pipe technology - gravel packing technology for pipe strings. The former mainly establishes a sand barrier within the wellbore using sand control pipes, while the latter

primarily relies on the compaction of gravel between the sand control pipe and the casing to block the flow of ceramsite, and also uses sand control pipes within the wellbore for sand prevention [19,20].

2.1.2. Chemical Sand Control

Chemical sand control is to inject chemicals into the loose formation and consolidate the formation sand body to achieve sand control. Generally, chemical sand control can be divided into three types [21, 22]: resin cemented formation sand, artificial well wall and other chemical solidified sand. It is the most utilized approach in oil and gas well due to its simple process flow, ease of utilization and treatment [23]. The chemical sand control approach can be artificial casing and artificial cementation approach [24]. The artificial casing approach entails introducing specific chemicals such as emulsified cement and water-mixed dry sand into the formation, while the artificial cementation method entails injecting specific chemical cementing reagents such as silicate or resin into the formation near the wellbore

2.1.3. Coking Sand Control

Coke sand control technology is mainly through heating the oil layer, so that the coke substance in the oil layer solidifies on the surface of the sand body, to improve the adhesion between the sand body and the sand body, and prevent the sand body migration. The commonly used coking methods include hot air injection for sand consolidation and short-term burning of oil reservoir for sand [25, 26] consolidation. The hot air injection for sand fixation entails injecting hot air into the wellbore to raise the temperature of the oil-layer, which prompts the coking of crude oil, while short-term in-situ combustion for oil layer sand fixation directly applies short-term fire to the oil layer, rapidly coking the crude oil within it.

2.1.4. Composite Sand Control

The commonly used coking methods include hot air injection for sand consolidation and shortterm burning of oil reservoir for sand [27,28] consolidation. Compound sand control technology is an organic combination of mechanical sand control and chemical sand control, through the establishment of a double sand barrier around the hole and on the tubing of the same oil well to achieve the purpose of sand control. The composite sand control technology can better solve the problem of the deficiency of single sand control technology, but it also has the characteristics [29,30] of complex process and poor economy.

2.2.Fracture Packing

Fracturing sand control technology has several merits in increase oil production and sand control. Post-fracturing fractures can effectively change the pressure distribution pattern and flow pattern around the well, it can be clearly seen from the figure that the high-pressure zone near the wellbore has been expanded after fracturing. The reduction of the pressure gradient can reduce the cost of displacement energy, thereby increasing the area of low pressure around the well and decontaminating some of the near-wellbore areas, this allows oil and gas that was originally difficult to reach the wellbore to flow smoothly [31]. The sand control through fracturing can be fracturing with resin sand as backup and fibre composite sand control. The follow-up resin control approach is a technical approach with good sand control impact developed on the basis of end sand removal fracturing [32,33,34] retention. For fibre composite approach, fibres are added to the proppant to strengthen the proppants within the fracture, reduces the chance of backflow, and helps prevent the formation of fine silt [35].

2.3.New Approaches

To meet the need for sand control in oil production, new sand approach have been rapid developed based on conventional sand and fracture filling sand control techniques, such as foam polymer resin diversion technology and zeta potential sand control technology.

2.3.1. Foam Polymer Resin Diverting Technology

A new approach of foam polymer resin shunt system based on chemical sand control was proposed by Srinath et al [36]. The system coupled with the features foam, improves viscosity and dispersion degree. When the shunt system is introduced into the formation, it flows into the more permeable region with the liquid flow, and the bubbles flow through the pores to produce a “Jamin effect”, which make the shunt system function as a low permeability layer to the formation. The shunt system can solidify aggregates of formation particles under the formation conditions, to increase reservoir drainage area, lower the longitudinal anisotropy of reservoir permeability and attain sand control.

2.3.2. Zeta Potential Sand Control Technology

Tahirov et al [37] introduced zeta potential changing system (ZPAS) into the formation to change the charge distribution on the surface of sands, starting from the control of Zeta potential between solid and liquid surfaces. By making the Zeta potential of the sandstone matrix within the range of +3-- -5mV, the electrostatic repulsion between sand particles and reservoir rocks is lowered, which encourages sand particles to aggregate into large clumps and move to reservoir rocks thus lowering sand migration [38]. Sand grain can move relative to each other without losing their ionic attraction forces and re-combine with change in stress in the reservoir. The injected chemical ZPAS does not impact formation wettability or permeability, but only alters the surface charge of the solid particles while being inert with other chemicals or minerals in the formation [38].

2.3.3. Digital Oilfield Technology

The need to effectively control sand, have led to the introduction of technologies such as digital oilfield (DOF) approach [39]. DOF is an interdisciplinary system as a virtual platform involving engineering, softwares, application, embedded systems, automation, information technology, business development, financing and process control for the integration, information technology, business development, design, planning, operations and management of all its activities vertically and horizontally across streams in order to optimize production, reduce downtime, ensure safety, minimize cost, eliminate time wastage, eliminate human error and unproductive actions as well as accelerate processes. DOF transmission is driven by the DARK technologies such as Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Extended Reality (XR) and Quantum Computing (QC). DLT enables secure and transparent record-keeping, streamlining processes like operations and project planning, logistics, supply chain management, scheduling, and financial transactions. AI aids automation across oilfield operations, data analysis, personalized customer experiences, operator learning, quality control and assurance, optimizing operations, time management, minimizing losses, improving production, efficiencies, enhanced reservoir modeling, improving metering and production allocation, and improving decision-making. XR, encompassing Virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), creates immersive experiences for training, entertainment, and product design, enhancing employee engagement and customer satisfaction. QC offers the potential for faster and more complex calculation, revolutionizing fields like drug discovery, materials science and financial modeling [40].

2.3.4. Surface Sand Control

The limitation of subsurface gas control systems such as technical viability, operational efficiency overtime and economic overhead, have led to the research and discovery of surface sand control system referred to Sand Trap [41]. The surface sand control is a piece of equipment for sand control in various applications, particularly in the oil and gas industrial [42]. Its primary function is separate sand and other solid component from a fluid stream to protect downstream assets from damage and prevent blockages, and it functions using the mechanism of gravity separation, centrifugal force and spherical design [43].

3.0. Conclusion

From the review study carried out, the following conclusion can be drawn

- (1) Sand production leads to erosion of downhole and surface facilities, accumulation at both downhole and surface facilities
- (2) Conventional sand control approaches such as chemical control, mechanical sand control, coking sand control and hybrid sand control technique, prevents sand production through different approach and can attain production sand specification
- (3) The fracturing and packing sand control technique has excellent technical viability and huge utilization prospects due to its properties of enhancing crude oil production and sand control.
- (4) Four kinds of fracturing packing technologies namely, end sand removal, fibre composite sand control, follow-up resin sand and fracture sand control blend, were identified as the progressive development in fracturing sand control technology.
- (5) Polymer-based solution such as Resin diversion technology, and nanoparticle based solution such as Zeta potential sand control were identified as the recent method of sand production control at the subsurface
- (6) Surface sand control system were identified as excellent sand control approach for high pressure reservoir due to its techno-economic capabilities
- (7) Digital Oilfield Technology approach is the best method of sand control, prediction and monitoring due to its multidisciplinary and technology-based nature.

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